

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL FACE SERUM AND COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT WITH MARKETED PRODUCT

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Article Received on 28 October 2025,
Article Revised on 17 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17735409>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Govind Reddy G., Ms. Anuruthya E.*, Mr. E. Maruti*, Ms. G. Anusha*, Ms. Geetha Yadav*, Mr. Goverdhan B*. (2025). Formulation and Evaluation Of Herbal Face Serum and Comparative Assessment With Marketed Product. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 842–859.

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ABSTRACT

Skin health plays a vital role in overall physical appearance and self-confidence. Among the most common dermatological concerns affecting individuals of all ages are acne, dark spots (hyperpigmentation), and wrinkles. These conditions not only reflect the physiological appearance but also indicates the skin's response to external and internal stressors. Acne primarily results from excessive sebum production, clogged pores, bacterial colonization, and inflammation of the pilosebaceous units. Hormonal fluctuations, genetics, poor skincare habits, and diet are major contributing factors. The lesions often heal with residual pigmentation or scarring, leading to uneven skin tone and texture. Dark spots, also known as post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) or age spots, occur due to overproduction of melanin by melanocytes. This process can be triggered by sun exposure, acne lesions, hormonal imbalance, or aging. Current management approaches include the use of topical agents such as hydroquinone, kojic acid, azelaic acid, niacinamide, and

retinoids. Wrinkles, are a hallmark of intrinsic and extrinsic aging. Intrinsic aging is a natural, genetically programmed process characterized by reduced collagen synthesis, loss of skin elasticity, and thinning of the epidermis. Extrinsic aging, commonly referred to as photoaging, results from chronic exposure to ultraviolet (UV) radiation, pollution, smoking, and oxidative stress. These external factors accelerate collagen degradation and damage

elastin fibres, leading to fine lines, sagging, and rough skin texture. Preventive measures such as sun protection, balanced diet, proper hydration, and antioxidant-rich skincare products play a crucial role in delaying the onset of wrinkles. In this present study herbal face serum was prepared for multipurpose, that is to treat acne, dark spots and wrinkles by using herbal extract such as flaxseed, green tea extract, aloe vera, and ascorbic acid(synthetic). The prepared formulations was showing better results in evaluation. This we came to know, when our formulation was compared with the marketed product. Here the marketed product which we have taken is of lotus company.

KEYWORDS: Acne, Dark spots, Hyperpigmentation, Wrinkles, flaxseed, green tea, ascorbic acid.

INTRODUCTION

SKIN

Skin is the body's largest organ, with a surface area of 2m². The skin comprises 15% of total adult body weight. Skin is a flexible and protective outer covering made of three layers the epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis that protects against pathogens, environmental damage, and trauma, while also regulating body temperature, facilitating sensation, and preventing water loss. It is composed of cells, glands, nerve endings, and blood vessels, and it forms part of the integumentary system along with hair, nails, and glands.

Fig. 01: Anatomy of skin.

TYPES OF SKIN

Every person has their own kind of skin type which includes Oily skin, Dry skin, Sensitive skin, Combination skin and Normal skin.

FUNCTIONS OF THE SKIN

Skin has the multiple function which includes Secretion, Heat regulation, Protection, Absorption, Elimination, Sensation, Vitamin D production, Melanin production etc.

ACNE

Acne is a chronic inflammatory skin disease that primarily affects the follicular sebaceous units. The highest incidence of acne occurs between the ages of 15 and 20. The prevalence of acne is relatively low among pre-adolescent children, and while it decreases after puberty. The pathogenesis of acne is complex and multifactorial, involving genetic predisposition, metabolism, hormone levels, environment, diet, immunity, etc.

Acne is projected to affect 9.4 % of the global population, ranking it eighth among skin diseases. Acne affects more than 85 % of teenagers, and the disease can persist into adulthood which often occurs in females and accounts for two-thirds of dermatologist consultations for acne.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF ACNE

Causes

Acne is primarily caused by clogged pores, which results from excess oil (sebum), dead skin cells, impurities, hormonal factors, lifestyle and environmental factors and medications side effects.

DARK SPOTS

Dark spots, also known as **hyperpigmentation**. These are the areas of skin that become darker than the surrounding skin due to an overproduction of melanin (skin's natural pigment).

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF DARK SPOTS

UV Radiation

Inflammation (acne, injury)

Hormonal changes (melasma)

CAUSES

Sun exposure, Hormonal changes, Acne and pimples, Skin inflammation, Aging, Certain medications, Genetic factors, Vitamin deficiencies, Excessive use of cosmetics and Pollution and toxins.

WRINKLES OR AGEING

Wrinkles are creases, lines, or folds that form on the skin, especially the face, neck, and hands, as part of the natural aging process or extrinsic factors like smoking, lifestyle, sunlight etc.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF WRINKLE

Intrinsic Aging (genetic, time-related)

CAUSES

Aging, Sun exposure, Loss of skin moisture, Repeated facial expressions, Genetics, Smoking, Poor nutrition, Pollution & toxins, Hormonal changes, Stress & poor sleep and Alcohol consumption.

TREATMENT

Here the treatment for all the skin concerned disease has almost same treatment such as topical antibiotics, systemic treatment, hormonal therapy, leaser therapy and cosmetic care.

In this present study herbal face serum (cosmetic care) was prepared for multipurpose, that is to treat acne, dark spots and wrinkles by using herbal extract such as flaxseed, green tea extract, aloe vera (smoothing agent), and ascorbic acid(synthetic).

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The ingredients used in herbal face serum preparation includes.

Flaxseed: It is obtained from the plant *linum usitatissimum*, belongs to *linaceae* family. Flaxseeds offer a wide range of health benefits due to their rich content of omega-3 fatty acids (ALA), fiber, protein, and lignans.

Fig. 02: Flaxseed.

Green tea: It is obtained from the leaves of plant *camellia Sinensis*, belongs to *Theaceae* family. It is rich in antioxidants, which can protect against cell damage, and its components may also help lower bad cholesterol, regulate blood sugar, and boost metabolism.

Fig. 03: Green tea leaves.

Ascorbic acid: Here synthetic ascorbic acid powder is used in the preparation of herbal face serum which is rich in vit-c (antioxidant).

Fig. 05: Ascorbic Acid.

Aloe vera: Aloe vera is the dried latex, or juice, collected from the leaves of the plant, specifically from the species *Aloe barbadensis*, belongs to *Liliaceae* family. It is used for skin health like moisturizing, wound healing, and treating burns etc.

Fig. 05: Aloe Vera

Rose water: It consist of geraniol component in it which is used as flavouring agent in the formulation.

Glycerin: glycerin is used as a humectant and it also acts as natural preservatives.

Sodium benzoate: It is used as a preservative due to its anti-microbial property.

Sodium bicarbonate: It is used as pH adjuster, which neutralizes acid to balance the skins pH value.

EXTRACTION METHOD

Extraction method of flaxseed

10gm of Flaxseed is weighed and rinse with distilled water then add 70 ml water to 10gm flaxseed and boil it for 7 min on a medium flame until gel forms. Strain it by using muslin cloth, cool it to room temperature.

IDENTIFICATION TEST FOR FLAXSEED GEL

1. Organoleptic properties

- **Odour** - mild, slightly nutty

- **Appearance** – transparent to pale yellow
- **Texture** – sticky, mucilaginous
- **Taste**- mild and neutral nutty

2. **Chemical test:** Identification test for omega-3-fatty acid and lignans.

TABLE

TEST	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1ml Bromine water+ 2ml flaxseed gel	Decolorization of brown color	Presence of omega-3-fatty acid

Ferric chloride test.

TEST	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1ml 1%Fecl ₃ solution+ 2ml flaxseed gel	Blue to dark green color	Presence of lignans compounds

Extraction method of green tea

Collection of green tea leaves and Shade drying should be done. Powdering of dried leaves, then 10 gm of dried leaves are weighed to that add ethanol in 1:10 ratio. Then collection of green tea extract.

IDENTIFICATION TEST FOR GREEN TEA

1. Organoleptic properties

Odour- mild, grassy aroma

Colour- yellowish to brownish green

Taste- astringent

2. **Chemical test:** Identification test for caffeine and catechin.

TEST	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Murexide test: 1ml sample+ 1 or 2 drops nitric acid + few drops ammonia	Purple colour	Presence of caffeine

TEST	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1 ml Ferric chloride solution+2 ml green tea extract	Black colour	EGCG Present

FORMULATION OF FACE SERUM

In a beaker take a 1.98ml extract of flax seed gel and 1ml green tea extract (mixture A). in another beaker gradually mix rose water, ascorbic acid, glycerin, and aloe vera gel (mixture B) Then mix both the mixtures, adjust the pH by using pH adjuster (sodium bicarbonate) the pH should be between 5.5-6.5, add preservative (sodium benzoate) and make up to the mark

with distilled water. Mix consistently to make a face serum. Herbal face serum is ready and subjected for further evaluation studies.

Ingredients	Category	Standard formula for 100ml	Formula for 10ml
Flaxseed gel	Natural polymer, emollient	19.8ml	1.98ml
Green tea extract	Antioxidant	10ml	1ml
Ascorbic acid	Brightening agent	12gm	1.2gm
Rose water	fragrance	18ml	1.8ml
Alovera gel	Soothing agent	20ml	2ml
Glycerin	humectant	5ml	0.5ml
Sodium benzoate	preservative	0.4g	0.04g
Distilled water	solvent	Qs	Qs to 10ml

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Evaluation parameters of water based facial serum containing flaxseed mucilage and green tea extract in two different formulations:

1. Drug-excipient compatibility study: FTIR can be used to investigate and predict any physiochemical interaction between different excipient. A physical mixture of drug and excipient was prepared.

The flaxseed and green tea were crushed and grinded separately. For sample preparation, the obtained fine powder is mixed with other excipients.

2. Visual appearance

The appearance of the formulations was considered visually.

3. pH determination

The equipment utilized was Digital pH meter, usually with a glass electrode. Once calibrating the apparatus with the standard buffer samples solution, the serum formulation was taken in a beaker, the electrode tip and junction should be completely submerged in the sample. Set the meter to begin taking a reading and the pH was measured.

4. Viscosity determination: Apparatus utilised here is Digital rotational viscometer.

Steps to be followed are

Selection of spindle – Spindle no.1 was used for the measurement of viscosity of all serums.

Sample container size – The viscosity was measured using 250ml of serum in 300 ml container.

- **Spindle immersion** – The spindle no.1 was lowered perpendicular in the centre taking care that spindle does not touch bottom of the jar.
- **Measurement of viscosity** – Spindle no.1 was used for determining the viscosity of the water-based serums. The factors like temperature, pressure and sample size, etc. which affect the viscosity was maintained during the process.
- After setting the viscometer, immerse the spindle into the serum and switch on the instrument. In display set up the spindle no., RPM and press the ‘OK’ button and check the viscosity of the serum.

5. Spreadability test

For the determination of Spreadability, 1gm of sample was applied between the two glass slides and was compressed to uniform thickness. A weight was added on upper plate and time required to separate the two slides, i.e. the time taken in which the upper slide moves over the lower slide was taken as measure of Spreadability.

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Where, **S** = Spreadability

M = weight applied on upper slide

L = length of glass slide moved by a sample

T = Time taken to separate slides

6. Drying time: a small amount of face serum was applied on the skin and gently massaged to find the drying time of the face serum.

7. Stability test: The prepared sample was kept under various condition to evaluate shelf-life of the facial serum.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identification test

1. Organoleptic properties: Test for flax seed gel

Test	Observation
Colour	transparent to pale yellow
Odour	Mild, slightly nutty
Taste	Mild and neutral nutty

2. Identification test for omega-3-fatty acid.

Test	Observation	Inference
1ml Bromine water+ 2ml flaxseed gel	Decolorization of brown colour	Presence of omega-3-fatty acid

3. Ferric chloride test for phenolic compound.

Test	Observation	Inference
1ml 1% FeCl ₃ solution+ 2ml flaxseed gel	Blue to dark green colour	Presence of phenolic compounds

Fig. 06: Decolourization of brown colour.

Fig. 07: Green colour.

Bromine water test was performed, we observed decolourization of brown colour, which confirms the presence of omega-3-fatty acid in mucilage.

To confirm the presence of phenolic compound like (secoisolariciresinol diglucoside) ferric chloride test was carried out, appearance of blue to dark green colour confirms the presence of phenolic compound that confirms the presence of phenolic compound.

By these results we can conclude that flaxseed mucilage contains main active ingredient.

B. Test for green tea extract

1. Organoleptic properties

Test	Observation
Colour	Yellowish to brownish green
Odour	Mild, grassy aroma
Taste	Astringent

2. Identification test for caffeine and catechins

TEST	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Murexide test: 1ml sample + 1 or 2 drops nitric acid + few drops ammonia	Purple colour	Presence of caffeine

TEST	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1 ml Ferric chloride solution +2 ml green tea extract	Black colour	EGCG Present

Fig. 08: Purple Colour.

Fig. 09: Black Colour.

Murexide test was carried out, we noticed purple colouration which indicates the presence of caffeine in the green tea extract.

Ferric chloride test was performed to confirm the presence of catechins (EGCG) by the black colouration.

By these results we can conclude that green tea extract contains active ingredient.

IR Spectroscopy of formulated herbal face serum

Fig.10: IR Spectroscopy of formulated herbal face serum.

Observed peak(cm^{-1})	Standard peak(cm^{-1})	Functional group
3200-3500	3400-3500	O-H stretching
2850-2950	2920-2850	C-H stretching
1700-1750	1740-1730	C=O stretching
1600-1650	1650-1630	C=C stretching
1200-1300	1250-1200	C-O stretching

VISUAL APPEARANCE

Formulation	Colour	Observation
Formulated Herbal face serum	Dark green	Clear, homogeneous free from lumps or sediments
Marketed face serum	Translucent	Clear and homogenous

The formulated water-based face serum appeared dark green in color, clear, and homogeneous, with a smooth texture and no visible lumps or sediments whereas marketed face serum was colorless and translucent, clear and homogenous.

pH DETERMINATION

Fig. 11: Formulated Face Serum.

Fig. 12: Marketed Face Serum.

Here the pH of the herbal water-based face serum is 5.44 and pH of marketed product is 5.53, which are Slightly acidic and suitable for skin.

SPREADABILITY

Fig. 13: Spreadability Test For Formulated Face Serum And Marketed Product.

$$S = M \times L / T$$

M = weight applied on upper slide (M) = 50g

L = length of glass slide moved by a sample (L) = 5cm

T = Time taken to separate slides (T) = 10 sec

$$S = 50 \times 5 / 10 = 25 \text{g.cm/sec}$$

- ❖ The calculated Spreadability value was found to be **25g.cm/sec** indicates that the serum has good spreadability allowing it to easily and uniformly cover the skin during application.
- ❖ Here both the formulated and marketed product are showing same value in the Spreadability test.

VISCOSITY

Fig. 14: Viscosity test for formulated face serum and marketed product at RPM 60.

Here at room temperature the viscosity for formulated face serum was showing 20mPa's at RPM 60 and for marketed product viscosity was showing 17mPa's at RPM 60. Here the instrument used is of Dolphin company. The spindle number which we have used was spindle no-0.

DRYING TIME TEST: Formulated herbal water-based face serum

Fig. 15: At time= 0min.

Fig. 16: At time= 3min.

Drying time test for marketed product**Fig. 18: At time= 2min**

The formulated water-based face serum dries on the skin within 3 minutes after application, leaving a smooth and non-sticky layer. Whereas the marketed product was taken 2 min to dry, so, from this we can conclude that the formulated face serum has good drying time.

WASHABILITY TEST: formulated water-based face serum**Fig. 20: Washability Test For Marketed Product.**

- The formulated water-based face serum and marketed product was found to be easily washable with water.
- No sticky residue or staining was observed, indicating good water solubility and ease of removal from the skin.

TLC TEST FOR CATECHIN

- **Rf factor** = distance travelled by the solute/distance travelled by the solvent
- $R_f = 1/5 = 0.20$

- **Stationary phase**= silica gel-G TLC plate
- **Mobile phase**= chloroform: ethyl acetate: GAA (4:4:2)

Fig. 21: TLC test for catechin.

STABILITY TESTING

Fig. 22: Storage condition at cold and room temperature.

The formulated face serum was observed at refrigerated condition (4°C) and at room temperature (37°C). At refrigerated there was no change in colour and odour of the formulation where as in the room temperature there was slightly change in colour but no change in odour hence it indicates that the product should be stored at lower temperature.

CONCLUSION

The water-based herbal face serum was successfully formulated using flaxseed and green tea extracts as natural actives. The formulation showed good Spreadability, Washability, and maintained an optimum skin-friendly pH of 5.5. It exhibited antioxidant and anti-aging benefits, supporting skin hydration and acne prevention. All evaluation results were within acceptable cosmetic standards, proving product stability and effectiveness. Thus, the herbal water-based serum can be considered a safe, natural, and affordable alternative to synthetic formulations.

FURTHER STUDIES

1. Clinical / Dermatological Testing: Test on volunteers for skin compatibility, irritation, and efficacy.
2. Penetration Studies: Evaluate absorption and bioavailability of active components on skin models.

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